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Mitochondriopathies - Short Report

PDH cytopathy: a consistently missed disease

Abstract

This brief report sheds light on PDH cytopathy, a rare metabolic disorder associated with a variety of clinical symptoms and metabolic disturbances. The symptoms can range from mild to severe lactic acidosis and may also include neurological, cardiac, hepatological, and reproductive disorders. This disorder affects the metabolism of pyruvate and glucose in cells and causes a shift from the citric acid cycle to glycolysis. There are several potential metabolic steps that can be pathologically altered, and these often lead to the same outcome.

The most common mutation demonstrates an X-linked semi-dominant inheritance. The symptoms are extremely diverse and the diagnosis is often difficult due to the complexity and heterogeneity of the disease. The gold standard for diagnosis remains the measurement of lactate levels in whole blood, both in the fasting state and after a sugar-rich meal.

So far, there is no evidence-based treatment for PDH cytopathy. Therapeutic approaches such as thiamine and Q10 are often recommended, and a reduction in sugar and carbohydrate load in the diet can be helpful. In diabetic patients with PDH cytopathy, strict control of blood sugar levels can be beneficial, although this is often difficult to achieve.

The PDH Cytopathy

Known as Pyruvate Dehydrogenase Deficiency, also known as PDH cytopathy, is a rare metabolic disorder on cell level (mitochondriopathy) that presents with a variety of clinical symptoms (syndrome) associated with metabolic disturbances, organ damage, and neurological symptoms. The symptoms range from mild to severe, even fatal lactic acidosis, to neurological, cardiological, hepatological, and reproductive disorders (in male patients). Although the disease has an extremely diverse symptom picture and can affect practically any organ, what is common to PDH cytopathies is that the metabolism of pyruvate and glucose in cells is disrupted. This results in a shift from the citric acid cycle to glycolysis, where lactate, not ATP, is the end product of glucose combustion. This has cascade-like and very far-reaching consequences for the entire metabolism. There are several defects in the subunits of the PDH complex and therefore, as known from mitochondrial diseases, there are several potential metabolic steps that can be pathologically altered, yet lead to the same clinical result.

Inheritance

The most common mutation shows an X-linked semi-dominant inheritance pattern, which can result in a woman with a defective X chromosome showing slightly abnormal lactate levels postprandially in the short term, without this leading to a clinically relevant PDH cytopathy (X-inactivation). However, as a mother, a woman can pass on the defective X

chromosome to a male descendant, who as a man with an X chromosome carries a not insignificant risk of developing PDH.

Clinical Presentation

Mitochondrial diseases in general, and also PDH cytopathy, are clinically, biochemically, and genetically heterogeneous and in most cases are characterized by a pronounced multi-systemic and fluid character. Even initially unspecific symptoms, especially those of the liver or the central nervous system, which seem to be unrelated at a cursory glance, can occur with PDH cytopathy. Due to the very high complexity and heterogeneity of the disease, diagnostic classification and clarification in suspected cases is often a challenge not to be underestimated, especially since the disease is considered rare.

Diagnostics

Due to the variety of symptoms and syndromes as well as inconsistent and difficult to standardize diagnostic paths, there is often uncertainty regarding the diagnostic procedure and diagnostic classification in adult patients. Experience has shown that this can lead to delays and also to repeated and unnecessary instrumental and laboratory medical examinations and other diagnostic measures if PDH cytopathy is not considered in the differential diagnosis. Even after the diagnosis, counseling and care of patients are often difficult, both in terms of genetic counseling and prognostic assessment and in terms of symptomatic treatment options. Limited

therapeutic options and the lack of curative treatments lead to increased individual therapeutic attempts, for which there are absolutely no evidence-based recommendations to this date. Diagnostic uncertainties and unfounded therapy attempts in the field of "mitochondrial medicine" can cause considerable additional costs in the health system and represent an unnecessary burden for the patients. Therefore, it is necessary to carefully plan and continuously evaluate the diagnostic and therapeutic approach in suspected or confirmed cases (usually already seriously ill) of mitochondrial diseases in adults.

Lactate as the leading parameter

As the gold standard, even before initiating modern genetic testing, the measurement of lactate levels in whole blood continues to apply, both in the fasting state and after a meal rich in sugar and other carbohydrates. In a healthy person, an increase in lactate levels of a maximum of 20% can be expected.

In contrast, people with clinically relevant PDH cytopathy have postprandial values between 4.0 and 6.0 mmol/l, often higher. Clinically healthy female carriers with X-inactivation show values up to around 3.5 mmol/l for a short time.

If the values correspond to the expected and the various genetically related family members can be tested, more complex human genetic diagnostics are often not necessary, unless family planning is an issue (human genetic counseling).

Treatment

To date (as of 2023), there is no evidence-based treatment for PDH cytopathy. Analogous to other mitochondrial diseases, thiamine (vitamin B1) and Q10 are sometimes recommended. Reducing the sugar and carbohydrate load in the diet can somewhat abbreviate the glycolytic state with its cascade-like consequences. In diabetics with PDH cytopathy, well-trained and experienced physicians can try to set the patient to low glucose target values, which often proves difficult.

Conflicts of Interest

None.

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